

PLAIN LANGUAGE STATEMENT AND CONSENT FORM

TO PARTICIPANTS

Plain Language Statement

Date: August 2021

Full Project Title: Human-centric Requirements Engineering for Artificial Intelligence Software Systems

Principal Researcher: A/Prof Mohamed Abdelrazek

Student Researcher: Khlood Ahmad

Associate Researcher(s): Dr. Muneera Bano, Dr. Chetan Arora, Professor John Grundy

Purpose of this research:

This survey contributes towards Khlood Ahmad's PhD thesis. The aim of this projects is to evaluate existing techniques and methods currently used by professional software engineers, data scientist and machine learning specialists when writing requirements for Artificial Intelligence (AI) powered software systems. This stage of the research is to get an insight from the experience and knowledge of experts from both the industry and educational institutes.

What the participation will involve:

If you consent to participate in this research, you will be asked to sit an anonymous online survey. Your participation is voluntary, and the survey will include a set of questions regarding your experiences with Requirements Engineering (RE) for AI systems. The survey should take approximately 10 to 15 minutes of your time.

The questions asked in this survey will include the following:

1. The first section will include general questions about your role in the organization, types of projects you have worked on, and years of experience. No identifying information such as name, age or contact details will be collected. These questions will help us find which are the most popular domains, and if the process of Requirements Engineering (RE) differs depending on the application domain. We also need to know how different roles conduct RE
2. The second section includes your experiences with Requirements / Modelling tools that you have used and what challenges or difficulties you have faced when writing requirements specifications for AI software.

3. The third section would be to identify current human-centric approaches you might have used to manage RE for AI (RE4AI) systems. These questions are based on guidelines taken from Google-PAIR, Apple, and Microsoft's human-centric guidelines for AI. You will help us identify which of these guidelines are involved in the Requirements Engineering phase, how many practices and which application domains focus on them most.

Risks and potential benefits to participants:

We do not anticipate any risk or potential benefit for any inconvenience or discomfort in participation other than the time spent participating in the survey.

Benefits to the wider community:

This research is focused on investigating current practices in requirements engineering for AI systems. Results collected from this study will help understand how requirements engineering is managed for AI software and what limitations and challenges exist from a human centric approach. This will provide us with insight into how we could improve current practices.

Privacy and confidentiality:

The survey is conducted via Qualtrics's secure online platform. Once the data is obtained it will be downloaded to a secure storage located on a local network at Deakin. We will not be collecting any identifiable data but if any is evident it will be removed to ensure your privacy.

Findings and results:

The findings of this study will be reported through peer-reviewed academic journals, conferences, and a PhD thesis. We will ensure that when the research results are published, we will not reveal your identity. If you wish to obtain a copy of our result's, please contact find our contact details below.

Sharing the data with others:

Data obtained from the survey will collected and accessed only be the named researchers and will not be shared with others.

Reimbursements/Incentives:

Unfortunately, no incentives or payment will be provided to you for completing this research.

Withdrawal:

Your participation is voluntary, and you may withdraw at any time while completing the survey. We will disregard any incomplete responses. However due to the anonymous nature of the survey and the absence of identifiable information you will not be possible to withdraw once the survey is submitted.

Funding:

N/A

Contact details of the researchers:

If you have any further questions regarding the study, please feel free to contact the research team regarding any queries:

- Mrs Khlood Ahmad. Deakin University. Phone: +61413319781. Email at: ahmadkhl@deakin.edu.au
- A/Prof. Mohamed Abdelrazek, School of Information Technology, Deakin University Melbourne Burwood Campus, 221 Burwood Highway, Burwood VIC 3125. Phone: +61 3 924 46140 or Email: mohamed.abdelrazek@deakin.edu.au

Complaints

If you have any complaints about any aspect of the project, the way it is being conducted or any questions about your rights as a research participant, then you may contact:

The Human Research Ethics Office, Deakin University, 221 Burwood Highway, Burwood Victoria 3125, Telephone: 9251 7129, research-ethics@deakin.edu.au

Please quote project number [SEBE-2021-41-MOD01].

Consent:

Consent will be established through the online form. You can only proceed to complete the survey once you have selected "yes" to give consent. Once you submit the survey, we will save your response and use only completed surveys for data collection.

By completing this survey, I agree that:

I have read, and I understand the attached Plain Language Statement.

I freely agree to participate in this project according to the conditions in the Plain Language Statement.

I have been given a copy of the Plain Language Statement and Consent Form to keep.

The researcher has agreed not to reveal my identity and personal details, including where information about this project is published, or presented in any public form.

I understand that the data used for this research will not be shared and information presented will be unidentifiable.